

EdicitNet

Integrating Edible City Solutions
for social, resilient & sustainably productive Cities

Transformations of
Human-Environment Systems

European
Commission

European
Commission

- **Deliverable 8.1**
 - Kick-Off Meeting of EdiCitNet Project 776665 from 19th to 21st of September 2018 in Berlin
 - Invitation of Target Groups:
 - Senator of Department of Development and Housing of Berlin
 - Mayors and Ambassadors or Embassy-related Persons of EdiCitNet Partner Cities
 - Consortia and Members of Advisory Board
 - European Commission Officers and Representatives

A short abstract about the Kick-Off Meeting...

We invited relevant persons for the EdiCitNet Kick-Off Meeting in order to publish it to relevant drivers and multipliers. A small stakeholder analyses guided the Coordination Team to the aforementioned audience. We divided the Kick-Off Meeting in three differently orientated days: The first day we called the „marriage“ – this day was meant to bring the people together to provide a familiar atmosphere that will foster trusting approach. Starting were several keynote speaker which introduced the topic and ended up with a small interactive performance of the coordinators. The second day was the „hard working“ day – our WP Leads (Executive Board) which prepared their WP session (in two parallel sessions- see Agenda) on a general and corporated designed template (see below), structured their tasks in subtasks allocated to person months of each partner and explained in detail the scope of their work package to their WP partners. A financial session was given by the EU Projectmanager from the Humboldt University of Berlin. The third day we called the „motivation and discussion“ day. Coordination and Management (WP8) was presented and the relevant structure in EdiCitNet. The presentation was followed by a vivid fishbowl discussion where the EdiCitNet Follower Cities could represent their challenges but also best practices in their cities.

EdiCitNet Kick-Off Meeting Agenda

19th – 21st of September 2018

Schedule

19th of September

11:30 Registration and Lunch

13:00 A warm welcome by the PI Ina Säumel

13:05 Keynote Speaker

13:15 Katrin Lompscher, Senator for Urban Development, Berlin

13:20 Keynote Speaker Announcement by Thomas Wachtel

13:35 Javier Peinado, Head of Sector Natural Resources, EASME

13:45 Marie Yeroyanni, Senior Expert in Innovating Cities, EC

13:50 Keynote Speaker Announcement by Suhana Reddy

13:55 Carsten Bredow, Managing Director Malzfabrik

14:00 All about EdiCitNet

14:15 Ina Säumel, Thomas Wachtel, Suhana Reddy

14:30 Coffee Break

14:35

14:45

14:55

15:05

15:15

15:25

15:30

- 15:45**
- 15:55**
- 16:05**
- 16:15**
- 16:25**
- 16:35**
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- 17:00**
- 18:30**
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20th of September

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08:30 Good Morning Coffee

09:00-10:30 WP 1 Session WP Session 2

10:30-11:00 Coffee Break

11:00-12:30 WP 3 Session

12:30-13:30 Lunch

13:30-15:00 WP 4 Session WP Session 6

15:00-15:30 Coffee Break

15:30-16:00 Laura Caniglia

Department for Research
Funding and Management

UBER

17:00-18:30 WP Session 7 WP 5 Session

18:30 Dinner

21st of September

- 10:00 ☑ **Good Morning Coffee** ☑
 - 10:30 ☑ **Presentation Project Management** ☑
 - 10:45 ☑ **Fishbowl discussion with Follower Cities at Market Place** ☑
 - 12:30 ☑ **Lunch** ☑
 - 13:30 ☑ **EdiCitNet Release by PI Ina Säumel** ☑
 - 14:00 ☑ **Good Bye Coffee** ☑
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Address and directions

Address

Malzfabrik
 Bessemerstrasse 2-14
 12103, Berlin
www.malzfabrik.de

Directions

The **Malzfabrik** is located within a 10-minute walk from the train station **Südkreuz**. This train station is well connected and easy to reach from all over Berlin. **Südkreuz** lies within the inner-city circle (District A+B if you buy a public transport ticket).

From the city centre Berlin Mitte:

(**Eriedrichstraße, Potsdamer Platz**) or **Gesundbrunnen**:
 S2 (direction **Blankenfelde**) and S25 (direction **Teltow**), stop at **Südkreuz**.

From the central station (Berlin Hauptbahnhof):

RE3 (Direction **Elsterwerda**), RE 4 (Direction **Jüterborg**) and RE 5 (Direction **Falkenberg**), stop at **Südkreuz**.

From **Ostkreuz (S41)** or **Westkreuz (S42)**:

The **Ringbahn** (Circle Line) S41/S42 stops at **Südkreuz**. The S41 runs clockwise, the S42 anti-clockwise.

Overview of Berlin's public transport connections:

European Commission represented
by Mmd. Maria Yeroyanni and M.
Javeir Peinado

Presentations of the EC...

Coordination Core Team...

Dipl. Social Geographer Mr.
Thomas Wachtel, HU Berlin

PI Mrs. Dr. Ina
Säumel, TU Berlin,
from 01.11.2018
HU Berlin

MSc. Project Manager
Mrs. Suhana Elisabeth
Reddy, TU Berlin, from
01.11.2018 HU Berlin

Senator Katrin Lompscher
Department
Development and
Housing of Berlin
Offering support
and
understanding of
the needs of this
project and is
focussed on the
recommendations
of the EC

Mr. Carsten Bredow, MD
Malzfabrik, special focus on
fostering green and
sustainable projects, cultural
heritage and green economy

Interactive role-play for emphasizing the need for action in this project...

Academia Key Message:
Enlarge the knowledge base.. but NGO
Keymessage: STOP the
research about evidence
and start to act!

Administration Key
Message: We have to
develop the structure
from scratch..

Innovation Action: Edible Cities Network

Act and REACT and try
to do things better...

Rotterdam Living Lab and Cities Administrative

Hands on and involvement of the guests and consortia

Vivid fishbowl discussion with
Follower Cities:
Needs, issues and barriers in
their Cities

Teambuilding Measure in the WP Groups:
Urban Farming in Berlin at Prinzessinnengärten

WP two session.. structure of all WP was equal according to the templates the Coordination team designed in advance...

All WP Leads prepared the template according to Template model from WP 7 (Lead Mr. Thomas Wachtel) (pls. ask for full version if needed)

Education, Knowledge Transfer and Dissemination

Work Plan - WP7

WP Lead (PM - person month)
UBER - Humboldt Universität Berlin (52) Prof. J. Niewöhner, Dipl. Geogr. Thomas Wachtel
WP Participants (PM)
TUB (21), ROTTERDAM (2), ANDERNACH (2), OSLO (2), HEIDELBERG (2), DDV (1), BHP (10), FSUB (4), TO (6), REACT (6), MUNDRAUB (10), NABOLAGSHÄGER (9), UOB (1), UL (3), UDG (6), ICAAI (2), RMIT EUROPE (2), PKU (2)
Processing Period
Month 1-60
Main Objectives
To guarantee broad societal anchoring of Edible City Solutions To develop and to realize comprehensive dissemination and exploitation measures To foster the development and encouragement of 'Communities of Practice'
Specific Objectives
To raise awareness for ECS and to enhance stakeholder's motivation To promote ECS knowledge transfer and to support skills on effective policy making To develop and implement an external communication strategy
Deliverables (deadline: date, month no.; responsible organization)
D 7.1 Refinement of plan for dissemination, communication and training activities (30.11.18, M3; UBER)
D 7.2 Public web site and online Community Platform (31.12.18, M4; TUB)
D 7.3 Data Management Plan (31.01.19, M5; UBER)
D 7.4 ECS curricula, webinar on ECS topic (31.07.20, M20 + update 31.07.23, M59; UBER)
D 7.5 Yearly ECS Forum, Conference and Summer School (31.08.19, M12; 31.08.20, M24; 31.08.21, M36; 31.08.22, M48; 31.08.23, M60; TUB)
Milestones
M5 11 First MOOC is online (30.04.2023, M56)

EdiCitNet - Edible Cities Network - Integrating Edible City Solutions for social resilient and sustainably productive cities
Kickoff Meeting Berlin, 17.-19.9.2018 in Berlin 1

Nearly the whole Citnet consortia...last day ending session foto

Annex to be send individually...

- We can provide more information about:
- the attendant guests plus guestlists
 - Template
 - Pictures
 - Sustainable give aways
 - the location and its special focus on sustainable, cultural heritage respecting business
 - detailed Work package sessions content